

LEARNING FUN THROUGH SENSOMOTORIK

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Abstract

Learning methods that process the sensory motor in all children. The process of Sensory motor in our view as Inclusion curriculum approach to a more modern approach to nature and we give naturally a normal proceed for both normal children and children who has difficulty, so that they later ready and capable of reading, writing, and counting. In the implementation of this process, the student brought in a play that it becomes his world; children's world is a world of play for inclusion or jointly between normal children and special need children. Limitation to know very basic maturity on the child should achieve at the age of 4, where all men are generally normal been able to enable the entire movement of rough and smooth motor And we Neuro Senso Institution also have prepared a basic value's tools . It could be we value on the completeness of Sensory motor all children , with Coordination competence. Who make it by playing while learning or learning by doing; the children that we prepare the very basic skills in advance have includes: 1) speed to respond something; (Body Awareness) 2) Have good concentration; 3) exercising self control; (Body Image) and 4) self-awareness about the time and place (body orientation) – they understand about how long, and where they are located. Sensory motor process optimize the development of a sensory system to function with full potential which is divided into three aspects, namely: 1) psychomotor; 2) audio motor; and 3) visual motor for age play 2.5 up to the age of 6 years old. Indeed the need of once sensory motor ambitions began to age an infant up to 6 year old children, that we can valued their ability of the children, to be able to enter into the world of reality and at the age of 4 years old child assessment, so that we can find the strength and weakness of the child, where the child is not too late if it should still be helped. And or starting to get developed talents and Gifted of children individually, because each child is unique:

With:

Psycho motor

A Learning system that aims to build a physical advances, the thoughts, and emotions as a whole (holistic). In other words, is to improve the psycho-socio-emotional of the child.

Audio motor

A Learning system that aims to specifically to enhance the concentration and motor planning also an orientation spaces, and improve children's overall communication skills.

Visual motor

A Learning system that aims specifically to help blend of fine motor coordination, rugged motor with eyes and ears, as well as to improve the development of cognition and perception of the child as a whole.

Keywords: sensory motor, kinesthetic, learning

The model of learning through Sensory motor:

This method is very well known and developed in developed countries as the most important part in education between age 1,5 to 7 years. With the coordination on the body movement we educate children through sensomotorik. It turns out that can help the child to sublimate thinking, learning potential and the potential the emotion better and also for those who are difficult to gather the energy to concentrate here, children will learn to be more focused. The experiences of the child aims to give a sense of selfreliance, the balance of psychological abuse, and also support as well as sharpen the mindset of a child. This kind of learning to be done gradually and regularly, particularly when done properly then after the meeting that to 8 will be seen a significant in behavior in children. Children will learn by itself to be able to find a balance between emotions and challenge energy through coordination of body movements of maturity of each child who gained from his experience. Through a learning method that we call the SENSORY MOTOR method of child learning, child activities and on the initiative of its own after the teacher give the right input appropriate funtion of their field. But it also may experience doesnt update the “tasty” right at her as a comparison. These experience make them learn to be “Bulletproof” and want to try, willing to fight with no winning, no crying spoiled. Article 6 the year 1999, the convention on the right of the child the unied nations, determines that”play is the right of every child.”

Learning Psycho Motor

Is a learning system that provides input on sporting gestures (kinesthetic) and aims to build the physical development, thoughts, and emotions, hardiness, in its entirety or holistically (As an increase in PSYCHO-SOCIO-EMOSIONAL children).

Learning Audio Motor

Is a learning system that aims specifically to develop and improve concentration of hearing that blends motor planning (train movements are planned), and the orientation of the time, it also improves the communication between teachers of children overall.

Learning Visual Motor

Is a learning system that aims to help blend the visual (eye) coordination, auditory (ear) with the output of the motor is smooth and rough, it also enhances the development of the perception of space cognition as a whole. The combination of the learning system like this we'll soon find in the children an interest to write down what they had heard. For this test the maturity of basic or now we mentioned in Kinder garden , children through this test we can see whether the child is ready or not, whether the child is gifted children, including sons of genius, or indigo at once in the course of entering primary school.

Definition of Sensory motor

The presence of a stimulus (input) on the remote or the sensory perception in inform Cortex (midbrain) that will be in supports by Hemisphere or cerebrum and then transmitted to the muscles as output or the human reaction. The purpose of training or sports activity throughout the Sensory motor body is a promotion of the quality of the child's IQ and EQ are optimal, obtained from: sensory system (remote) that is honed. To able to develop the whole coordination . Accompanied by strategies, mindsets (the perception) and awareness of the body (Body Awareness) is good too. Keep in mind, that: the processing of the program sensory motor which is also referred to as training activity though proper body in place in schools, which can be started from age play group up to the age of teenagers, is one of the important subjects in the curriculum (Flemming, 1968). With the appearance of the physical condition and coordination body that was routed on the child, who comes from a good body motion activity, will provide a positive influence on a child's ability to communicate, on the ability of children's cognition, in addressing the various issues that arise in him, especially in the way he interacts with others (Herm,1997).

The program sensory motor can also help children develop integrity to bring up the power of creativity and also can to improve himself into his academic ability. Basic capabilities that must exist on all children, namely: the speed of responding to something. Able to concentrate. To be able to practice self control. Children selfconsciousness about time and place (Body Orientation), when, how long and where they are located.

Our Sensory motor motto is :

From nothing into being (is more about thought provoking associations, as well as eliciting activities our Sensory as capital social rationale)

From can't be can (which is a coordination of the brain, which collect and arrange to be knit social thought which comes from his experience)

From the unusual becomes Regular (which is the integration of the brain, which is repeat and organizing various knit social thought that is already formed/coding system).

Conclusion:

Of all the situations that happen every day at this time on our Earth, our determination as a Sensory motor Community became round. Problem solving skills helpful in the treatment of functional movement and sensory processing problems in children with developmental disabilities. Neuro-holistic, blended approach will weave together concepts of sensory processing intervention together with Neuro-Developmental Treatment (NDT), widening the lens of assessment and treatment possibilities. Lecture, lab and videotape analysis will deepen this learning opportunity.

Learning Objectives:

Upon completion of this workshop, participants will be able to:

- Identify sensory processing difficulties and their relationship to movement and behaviour in children with a variety of disorders.
- Analyze postural and movement patterns and their relationship to sensory processing.
- Weave together a blending of NDT and SI concepts within treatment.
- Use blending approaches in the context of the child's and family's occupation
- Use the evidence to support clinical practice.

The above text summarizes and descriptively demonstrates the main instructions for writing and preparing the full paper. All that is missing now are guidelines regarding references. Therapists providing intervention to children with movement challenges have traditionally considered and have perhaps treated “muscle tone” specifically as an impairment impeding motor performance in daily living function. In our hands, we can “feel” the resistance, heaviness, responsiveness and changes of each child’s body with whom we interface in therapy. Our own motor system learns and remembers how each child’s limbs and body feel in the various positions we place them in and during the movement experience to be provide them.

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